

Investigations concerning the Synthesis of Condensed Furanopyrazoles, Furanodiazepines and Furanooxazepines starting with 3-Chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde. Part-IV

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3-Chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (2) on condensation with a variety of nitrogen dinucleophiles gave the expected aldimines (3a-d, 4a-d, 5). Attempted intramolecular cyclisation under the influence of acid or base catalysis or thermolysis or even photolysis of these aldimines (3a-d, 4a-d, 5) was however found to be unsuccessful. Even the chloroacetal (12) prepared from the chloroaldehyde (2) failed to undergo substitution of the halogen by the nitrogen nucleophiles in affording the corresponding substituted acetal (13). The tosylate (16) derived from the aldimine (5) also failed to undergo intramolecular cyclisation in furnishing the anticipated seven-membered heterocyclic derivative (17).

THE contraceptive, abortifacient and antihypertensive activities exhibited by pyrazolobenzocycloalkanes¹ and antianxiolytic activity exhibited by benzodiazepines², benzoxazepine derivatives prompted us to investigate the feasibility of the synthesis of 6-methoxy-benzofuro[2,3-c]pyrazole (6b), 6-methoxybenzofuro[3,2-b][1,5]benzodiazepine (8), 6-methoxybenzofuro[2,3-f]-1,4-oxazepine (7a) from 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (2) (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer with SiMe₄ as an internal standard. Microanalytical data were determined at the Department of Chemistry, I.I.T., Madras.

Aldimine or aldoximes (3a-d, 4a-d, 5) derived from 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (2): A mixture of 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (1.05 g, 5 mmol) and dinucleophile (5 mmol) in ethanol (25 ml) was stirred for 30 min at room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residual solid was filtered and dried. Recrystallisation from carbon tetrachloride gave analytically pure samples of aldimines and aldoximes as pale yellow crystalline solids (Table 1).

3-Chloro-2-(1,3-dioxolan-2-yl)-6-methoxybenzofuran (12): A solution of 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (1.05 g, 5 mmol) in dry benzene (50 ml) containing ethylene glycol (1.13 g, 16 mmol) and a crystal of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid was

Scheme 1

refluxed for 5 h using a Dean-Stark water separator. The cooled solution was washed with saturated

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) cm^{-1}	δ (CDCl_3)	(m/δ) (M^+)
3a	65	156–58	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClNO}_2$	3 900 (OH), 1 630–1 640 (C–N)	3.7 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 6.5–7.2 (3H, m, ArH), 7.9 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	225
3b	70	126–27	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 400 (NH_2)	3.8 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 5.7 (1H, s, NH_2), 6.7–7.3 (3H, m, ArH), 7.6 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	224
3c	60	139–40	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 200 (NH), 1 620 (C=N)	3.84 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 4.71 (1H, s, NH), 6.8–7.46 (8H, m, ArH), 7.56 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	300
3d	75	168–69	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$	3 180 (NH), 1 620 (C=N)	2.37 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.92 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 7.0–7.8 (7H, m, ArH), 7.93 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$), 11.43 (1H, s, NH)	378
4a	85	86–7	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClNO}_2$	3 900 (OH)	3.8 (7H, s, ArOCH_3 and $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 6.7–7.3 (3H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	253
4b	82	161–68	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 400 (NH_2)	3.9 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 3.7 (4H, s, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$), 6.6–7.3 (4H, m, ArH), 8.0 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	252
4c	65	88–9	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 400 (NH_2), 1 620 (C=N)	1.82 (6H, s, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_2$), 3.84 (6H, s, ArOCH_3), 4.97 (1H, s, NH_2), 6.98–7.34 (3H, m, ArH), 8.38 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	266
4d	68	120–21	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 200 (NH_2)	1.70–1.90 (4H, m, $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-\text{N}$), 3.89 (7H, s, ArOCH_3 and $\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$), 7.01–7.39 (3H, m, ArH), 8.32 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	280
5	86	128–30	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_2$	3 500–3 400 (NH_2)	3.7 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 4.3 (1H, s, NH_2), 6.7–7.4 (7H, m, ArH), 8.7 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$)	300
12	70	82–4	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClO}_4$	1 600 (C=O)	3.79 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 4.11 (4H, d, $\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}$), 6.19 (1H, s, OCHO), 6.96–7.36 (3H, m, ArH)	254
14	60	68–70	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClNO}_2$	3 500–3 200 (OH, NH)	3.63–3.73 (9H, s, ArOCH_3 and $\text{CH}_2\text{NHCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$), 6.87–7.3 (3H, m, ArH)	255
17	40	178–79	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_7\text{S}$	1 620 (C=N)	2.41 (3H, s, ArCH_3), 3.39 (3H, s, ArOCH_3), 6.95–7.67 (11H, m, ArH), 8.24 (1H, s, $\text{OH}=\text{N}$), 9.88 (1H, s, NHSO_3Ar)	454

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

sodium bicarbonate solution (3×10 ml) and water, and dried over sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the solvent gave a orange yellow solid. Repeated recrystallisation from hexane gave analytically pure sample of the acetal (**12**; 0.88 g) as a light yellow solid (Table 1).

2-[[(3-Chloro-6-methoxy-2-benzofuranyl)methyl]amino]ethanol (**14**): A solution of the bicyclic aldimine (**4a**; 1.27 g, 5 mmol) and sodium borohydride (0.15 g, 4 mmol) in methanol (25 ml) was stirred at 10° for 10 min. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for further 30 min. The solvent was then distilled off and the dark brown residue was triturated with water (25 ml). The resulting residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (4×20 ml) and the extracts were dried over sodium sulphate and evaporated to yield a gummy brown solid. Recrystallisation from carbon tetrachloride gave dihydro

derivative as light brown crystalline solid (**14**; 0.76 g) (Table 1).

N-[2-[[(3-Chloro-6-methoxy-2-benzofuranyl)methylene]amino]phenyl-4-methylbenzene sulphonamide (**16**): A solution of the bicyclic aldimine (**5**; 1.5 g, 5 mmol) and *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (0.95 g, 5 mmol) in dry pyridine (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solvent was distilled off and the dark brown residue was poured into ice-cold dilute HCl (50 ml). The resulting residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (4×20 ml) and extracts were thoroughly washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate, and evaporated to yield a gummy solid. The crude product was chromatographed on a column of silica gel (80 g). Hexane–ethyl acetate (9:1) eluates gave analytically pure sample of *N*-tosylate (**16**; 0.83 g) as a light brown solid (Table 1).

Coppola³ reported the synthesis of 2-chloro-3-benzofurancarboxaldehyde by the Vilsmeier-Haack reaction of 2-coumaranone and the major product (46%) was identified as the expected 2-chloro-3-benzofuran carboxaldehyde. However, when 6-methoxy-3-coumaranone (**1**; Scheme 1) was subjected to Vilsmeier-Haack reaction it furnished the expected 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde (**2**) as the exclusive product (60%) as reported from these laboratories⁴. These chloroaldehydes were earlier used in the building up of new types of fused sulphur heterocycles by us^{4,5}. A number of attempts, as discussed below have been studied in order to obtain the aforementioned pyrazole (**6b**), diazepine (**8**) and oxazepine (**7a**) derivatives. In the present investigation, 3-chloro-6-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxaldehyde, was condensed with a variety of dinucleophiles such as hydrazine, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, phenylhydrazine, tosylhydrazine, ethanolamine, ethylenediamine, 1,3-diaminopropane, 1,4-diaminobutane and *o*-phenylenediamine in ethanol with a view to obtaining the tri- and tetracyclic heterocycles (**6a-d**, **7a-d** and **8**) as depicted in Scheme 1.

In all these attempts, the reaction afforded only the corresponding Schiff bases (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) as the end products. The structures assigned to these Schiff bases were based on spectral and analytical data. The ir spectra of the aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) indicated two bands at 3 500–3 200 and 1 630 cm^{-1} corresponding to the OH or NH stretching and C=N stretching respectively. The ¹H nmr spectra of these Schiff bases showed the azomethine proton at δ 7.7–8.3 in addition to the other anticipated proton signals (Table 1). Most surprisingly the attempted intramolecular displacement of chlorine in these aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) under a variety of conditions was found to be unsuccessful. For example use of protonic acid catalysts such as (i) PTS in refluxing benzene, (ii) super acid such as Nafion H⁶ in refluxing benzene and (iii) methanolic HCl have been found to be of no avail.

Protonation of the iminic bond (C=N) initially by the acidic catalysts is expected to promote the intramolecular cyclisation but it was, however, noticed to be ineffective. It may be recalled that structurally similar systems (**10**) reported earlier by Moorthy *et al.*⁷ have been undergone successfully the desired intramolecular nucleophilic displacement to give rise to the desired coumarinoisoxazole derivative (**11**; Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Treatment of the aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) with sodium methoxide in methanol or anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetonitrile was also found

to be ineffective in furnishing the desired products (**6a-d**, **7a-d**, **8**). Thermolysis of the aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) was effected by refluxing the same in orthodichlorobenzene, leading to the recovery of the starting material. Even the photolysis⁸ of the aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) in acetone in presence of triethylamine also led to the recovery of unreacted starting compound in each case.

The probable reason for the observed difficulty in the cyclisation of these aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**) to furnish the expected heterocycles (**6a-d**, **7a-d**, **8**) may be attributed to the unfavourable *E*-configuration of the iminic double bond (C=N). It is thought that the presence of acid catalysts could lead to initial protonation of the iminic bond and consequently allow the facile cyclisation. Even under these conditions, the anticipated heterocycles could not be obtained. In some instances intractable materials were isolated.

Conversion of β -chloroaldehyde (**2**) into the corresponding acetal (**12**; Scheme 3) was effected with a view to achieving the substitution of the chlorine following the procedure of Cohn and Hayes⁹. Attempted nucleophilic substitution of chlorine in the acetal (**12**) by the various nitrogen nucleophiles was also found to be unsuccessful. In view of the difficulties encountered in the above discussed intramolecular displacement reactions of chlorine in the aldimines (**3a-d**, **4a-d**, **5**), it was felt advantageous to attempt the displacement of chlorine after saturating the imine double bond, thereby providing a free rotation of the C–N bond would facilitate the intramolecular displacement of chlorine by the nitrogen nucleophiles. With this end in view, the aldimine (**4a**; Scheme 3) was reduced to the corresponding dihydro derivative (**14**) with sodium borohydride. The structure assigned to **14** was based on analytical and spectral data. Attempted cyclisation of **14**, to obtain the desired heterocycle (**15**; Scheme 3) adopting the procedure reported by Nielson and Pederson¹⁰, was also found to be in vain.

Scheme 3

In order to increase the reactivity of the NH_2 function in the aldimines and thereby activating the process of intramolecular displacement of chlorine, the tosylate derivative (16) was prepared. Attempted base-catalysed intramolecular cyclisation of the tosylate derivative (16) was also found to be unsuccessful in furnishing the fused 1,5-benzodiazepine derivative (17). In view of the above difficulties experienced in the displacement of chlorine by direct and indirect routes, the syntheses of the anticipated tricyclic and tetracyclic fused heterocycles could not be achieved.

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